

Partial sum of binomial coefficients

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Abstract

In this note we present an explicit formula for the partial sum of binomial coefficients, i.e.

$$\sum_{k=k_0}^{k_f} \binom{n}{k},$$

where both n and k can be integer or fractional, positive or negative numbers.

The only condition is that the difference $k_0 - k_f$ is an integer number, because we have to go from k_0 to k_f in a finite number of steps.

The formula is:

$$\sum_{k=k_0}^{k_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n}{k_0} \times \left\{ 1 + \frac{m}{k_0 + 1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{k_0 + 2} \left(1 + \frac{m-2}{k_0 + 3} \dots \left(1 + \frac{n+1-k_f}{k_f} \right) \right) \right) \right\}$$

where $m = n - k_0$

- From the standard definition of binomial $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ we have the identity

$$1) \quad \binom{n}{k+t} = \binom{n}{k+t-1} * \frac{n-k-t+1}{k+t}$$

indeed

$$\frac{n!}{(k+t)!(n-k-t)!} = \frac{n!}{(k+t-1)!(n-k-t+1)!} * \frac{n-k-t+1}{k+t}$$

i.e.

$$\frac{n!}{(n-k-t)!} = \frac{n!}{(n-k-t)!} \quad \text{QED}$$

- Let $k = k_0$ and $m = n - k_0$, using the 1) we have:

$$\binom{n}{k_0+1} = \binom{n}{k_0} * \frac{m}{k_0+1},$$

$$\binom{n}{k_0+2} = \binom{n}{k_0+1} * \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} = \binom{n}{k_0} * \frac{m}{k_0+1} * \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} \quad \text{and so on.}$$

The sum is:

$$\binom{n}{k_0} + \binom{n}{k_0+1} + \binom{n}{k_0+2} + \dots + \binom{n}{k_f} = \binom{n}{k_0} + \binom{n}{k_0} * \frac{m}{k_0+1} + \binom{n}{k_0} * \frac{m}{k_0+1} * \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} + \dots$$

and so:

2)

$$\sum_{k=k_0}^{k_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n}{k_0} \times \left\{ 1 + \frac{m}{k_0+1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} \left(1 + \frac{m-2}{k_0+3} \dots \left(1 + \frac{n+1-k_f}{k_f} \right) \right) \right) \right\}$$

- A very simple example is:

Let $n = 7$, $k_0 = 2$, and $k_f = 6$, i.e. $\binom{7}{2} + \binom{7}{3} + \binom{7}{4} + \binom{7}{5} + \binom{7}{6} = 119$

from the 2) we have

$$\sum_{k=2}^6 \binom{7}{k} = \binom{7}{2} * \left\{ 1 + \frac{5}{2+1} \left(1 + \frac{5-1}{2+2} \left(1 + \frac{5-2}{2+3} \left(1 + \frac{5-3}{2+4} \right) \right) \right) \right\} = 21 * \frac{17}{3} = 119$$

- A more complex example is:

Let $n = 5.5$, $k_0 = 1/3$, and $k_f = 25/3$ and so $m = 31/6$

$$\sum_{k=\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{25}{3}} \binom{5.5}{k} = \binom{5.5}{\frac{1}{3}} * \left\{ 1 + \frac{31}{8} * \left(1 + \frac{25}{14} * \left(1 + \frac{19}{20} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{7}{32} \left(1 + \frac{1}{38} \left(1 - \frac{5}{44} \left(1 - \frac{11}{50} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right\} = \binom{5.5}{\frac{1}{3}} * 22.39137189 = 45.15455985$$

where $\binom{5.5}{1/3} = \frac{5.5!}{(1/3)! * (\frac{31}{6})!} = 2.016605328$

- In general, the increment of the sum could be different from 1. As an example, let the increment be 2, then the formula 2) becomes:

2 bis)

$$\sum_{k=k_0,2}^{k_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n}{k_0} * \left\{ 1 + \frac{m}{k_0+1} * \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} \left(1 + \frac{m-2}{k_0+3} * \frac{m-3}{k_0+4} (1 + \dots) \right) \right\}$$

E.g. let $n = 10$, $k_0 = 2$, and $k_f = 6$, then

$$\sum_{k=2,2}^6 \binom{10}{k} = \binom{10}{2} + \binom{10}{4} + \binom{10}{6} = 45 + 210 + 210 = 465$$

Using 2 bis) we have

$$\binom{10}{2} * \left\{ 1 + \frac{8*7}{3*4} \left(1 + \frac{6*5}{5*6} \right) \right\} = 45 * \left(1 + \frac{56}{12} (1 + 1) \right) = 465$$

- It is quite easy to program the formula 2), e.g. using the Python language we have

```
from numpy import *
from scipy.special import *

def sumkn( n, k0, kf):
```

```
m = n-k0
s = 1
for i in arange(kf-k0, 0, -1):
    s = 1 + (m-i+1) / (k0+i)*s
res = s * binom(n, k0)
return res
```